

Shoe and Bag Skill Acquisition in Aba, Nigeria: Panacea for Sustainable Economic Development

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Abstract

This study examines the critical role of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in promoting sustainable economic development in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. Focusing on practical TVET models in the local shoe and bag production industry, it explores how skill-based education empowers young people to become self-reliant entrepreneurs, thereby reducing unemployment and stimulating long-term growth. A cross-sectional research design was adopted, with data drawn from three purposively selected industries in the Aba leather market. Time-series enrolment data were analysed statistically to provide insights into youth employment trends. Chi-square analysis was applied to examine employment rates, economic growth, and projected youth employment by 2030, given its strength in assessing probability-based relationships. Findings revealed a substantial yearly employment increase of 53.8% between 2020 and 2024, with a projected probability rise of 26.9% ($\chi^2 = 26.9$) by 2030. These results highlight TVET's effectiveness in equipping youth with practical skills and bridging the gap between formal education and industry needs. Socially, enhanced TVET programmes promote inclusion by reducing unemployment and poverty, particularly among women and rural populations. Practically, the findings provide policymakers, educators, and industry leaders with evidence to strengthen TVET systems in Aba, aligning them with evolving technologies and market demands. Overall, the study underscores TVET's transformative potential as a driver of entrepreneurship, self-reliance, and sustainable development in Nigeria

Keywords: Aba TVET model, Youth empowerment, Sustainable Economic development, Vocational Training, Skill Acquisition

Introduction

In Addressing challenges like poverty, inequality, and resource depletion goes with structuring informal skill-based models that will equip the youth and promote sustainable practices in different areas like shoe and bag production. This practical skill-based models are essential for creating more employment opportunities for the young people and stand as a viable industry for training and learning. Integrating this form of skill-based training and learning requires a good number of apprenticeships equal to school-based learning (Frommberger, 2024), from different urban and rural areas.

Nigeria is one of the developing countries that its needs, prospects and challenges call for vital attention to sustainable development strategies as its population is close to about 220 million as projected population figure for Nigeria in 2022 was 216,783,381 (Adeniran, 2023). Moreover, sustainable development Goals (SDGs) agenda in Nigeria covered 169 priorities (Adeniran, 2023), with prospects reaching the year 2030. However, these sets of goals require equipping the youth with more practical skill-based models to maintain and sustain their competence to fulfil their own needs by the year 2030 and beyond. Nevertheless, human and material resources for practical skill-based training models in Nigeria seem to suffer limited funding, emissions and other similar challenges hindering its viability. There is always challenge in balancing the skill-based training with school-based learning considering the fact that a good number of apprenticeships are needed for the former. However, expanding TVET structures in shoe and bag production in Nigeria with emerging technological trends would foster a mind-set shift and prepare a good number of Nigerian youths to acquire sustained competence for long-term sustainable and economic development. The interest of state and private sectors' approach is needed in such structure.

The shoe and bag production industry in Aba, Abia State Nigeria, is a significant industry, with the federal and state governments recognizing its economic importance. It is considered a tool for state economic development. The industry is recently estimated to involve over 500,000 artisans (Onyekwelu, 2025), highlighting its substantial workforce. The government's support aims at boosting the economy and fostering entrepreneurship; suggests a focus on local production, job creation, and import substitution. Considering the key challenges, however, producing a pair of shoes takes between one and two weeks, but doing the same in China takes two to three days for obvious reasons (Onyekwelu, 2025). A sophisticated shoe soles machine seen on Alibaba.com costs \$2,999 which can perform the shoe-gumming function within minutes, but Aba shoemakers manage to perform this with bare hands or by the use of gum and hammer. This model's success depends on its ability to adopt a diverse context to promote continuous improvement, and integrate theoretical knowledge with practical application. A well-designed structured TVET with the collaboration of the government and private sectors is critically needed in these trades for sustainable economic development and growth in Nigeria.

However, this research anchor on Holland's theory of career choice (Holland, 1997) which proposes that people achieve career satisfaction and success when their personal characteristics and interests are congruent with their work environment. This is based on six personality and work environment types, known by the RIASEC model: Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional. This theory suggests matching individuals to compatible career paths to promote positive outcomes. Exposure to shoe and bag training programmes can strengthened young people's interest to learn and fit in the market demand. Using this theory which states that people seek work environments that fit their vocational interests in order to be satisfied and successful (Hartmann et al., 2021). The Holland Codes, central to John Holland's theory of career choice, suggest that individuals are best suited to careers that align with their personality. Thus, there is need for a structured TVET training on these aforementioned models. As the theory identifies six personality types: Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional (RIASEC). Young people would tend to seek work environments that match their dominant personality type. For example, a person high in 'Investigative' traits might thrive in a research-oriented role, while someone with 'Enterprising' characteristics may excel in a management position. Training young people to understand their Holland Code can help guide career exploration and decision-making, leading to increased job creation, continuum and success.

Problem statement

Youth unemployment is a significant challenge in the contemporary Nigeria. Lack of practical skills and experience, coupled with inadequate career guidance and training exacerbate this problem. Addressing youth unemployment requires a multifaceted approach, including strengthening vocational education and training program in shoe and bag production to promote entrepreneurship and ensuring that education and training programs are aligned with the market demands. Aba shoe and bag production located at Abia state is one among the major competing skill-based models in Nigeria. This practical skill-based model is capable of competing with production of good useful within and outside the country compared with its China production for the export market (Anudu, 2019). However, Aba's industrial city has suffered several challenges including poor infrastructure, connectivity to major market hubs, government neglect of its potential, and the inability to ascend beyond artisanal manufacturing to a modern medium to large scale industrial hub. Aba's potential remains untapped as a leading hub on SME integration into the wider global market, especially through the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). For instance, China has a comparative advantage in renewable energy, which helps its manufacturers to produce cheap goods, including shoes. If such can be strengthened and structured in this particular reference model, sustainable economic development is assured. There is need for practical structured model in this factory production area to empower the for long-term economic growth. Aljazeera news of 4th May, 2020 reported that 40% of Nigerians live below the poverty

line. Nuhu (2022) suggested that one potential remedy lies in the acquisition of relevant vocational/technical and entrepreneurship skills among the populace, that it would enable them to become self-reliant and contribute meaningfully to the Nigerian economy. While accepting such suggestion there is need to structure the already existing models in Aba, Abia state Nigeria to attract peoples' perceptions and behavioural disposition. Establishing policy that will direct youth attention to such production and viable remuneration in that policy would witness higher employment rates and economic progress in return.

Purpose of the study

This study aims at exploring the critical role of TVET in driving sustainable economic development in Nigeria focusing on Aba shoe and bag production industry. The following research questions were put forward to be answered.

Research questions

1. How does Aba shoe and bag production industry foster economic growth in Nigeria?
2. To what extent does Aba shoe and bag production impact employment rate in Nigeria?
3. How does this practical TVET models foster long-term economic growth and development in Nigeria?

Research objectives

The following are the research objectives.

1. To evaluate TEVT implementation in Nigeria with particular reference to Aba shoe and bag production industry.
2. To assess the impact of Aba shoe and bag production on employment rate in Nigeria.
3. To assess how this practical TVET models can foster long-term economic growth and development in Nigeria.

Method of data collection

The study adopted a cross-sectional research design with data drawn from Aba shoe and bag production industry. Three industries were sampled using purposive sampling techniques, time series enrolment data were gathered through report from the president of leather association and were used for statistical analysis. Case studies from Aba leather market production industry provide contextual analysis of TVET implementation. Chi-square analysis was used to answer the research questions projecting youth employment rate, economic growth and expected youth

employment rate by the year 2030. This statistic was chosen because it allows one to answer significant problem with tests of probability.

Research question 1. How does Aba shoe and bag production industry foster economic growth in Nigeria? Aba leather market production industry provide contextual analysis of the TVET implementation in the country.

Image 1 shoe production

Source: <https://businessday.ng/news/article/son-to-standardise-aba-made-shoes-garments-others/>
Aba, has the largest concentration of micro, small and medium-scale enterprises (MSMEs) in the country with a sizable number engaged in tailoring and finished leather products such as shoes, belts and bags. The mass production capacities of component clusters of Aba Industrial City and similar models are capable of positioning Nigeria at a competitive advantage in the global garment and leather industrial space. In 2016, the Textile, Apparel, and Footwear sector contributed N7 trillion (\$7,078,540,953), exactly 2.1% of Nigeria's total GDP, to Nigeria's economy (NBS, 2020). Structured skill-based acquisition not degrees is needed in driving sustain economic development in Nigeria (Ali, 2022).

Image 2 the leather shoe

Source: <https://punchng.com/aba-leather-industry-made-in-nigeria-brand-waiting-for-govtslifeline/>

Skills, rather than degrees, can significantly enhance social inclusion by providing individuals with practical abilities that are valued in various settings (Ali, 2022). Structured programmes in this industry, for example, can improve social mobility and inclusion. Focusing on skills can help reduce social exclusion and support diverse groups, including those with disabilities, by providing them with opportunities to participate fully in society regardless of their educational level.

Image 3. Bag production

Source: <https://web.facebook.com/groups/3407725656119204/>

Aba bag production contributes to local economic growth. Different sizes of bags such as school, travelling, shopping, and men's bags are produced in Aba. Lady's handbags and school children's bags and buyers want them worldwide. In Nigeria, focusing on skills acquisition in bag production rather than solely emphasizing on degrees can significantly reduce unemployment and drive economic growth by making individuals more employable, empowering them to become self-reliant entrepreneurs, and contributing to the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is a powerful tool for bridging the skills gap and empowering youth, particularly in developing economies (Zhang, 2024).

Focusing on practical job-relevant skills, TVET programs can equip young people with the knowledge and abilities needed to enter the workforce and contribute to economic growth. The case skill-based model used in this research is an informal, artisan-based shoe and bags production industry centered in Aba, Nigeria, where a large number of artisans, primarily small-scale with mostly age ranged from 20 to 40 years receive training and being trained. The model produces a wide variety of shoes, and bags. This model is characterized by its decentralized nature, reliance on traditional skills, and a focus on local materials and markets, with a growing emphasis on innovation and technology.

Statistical insight in Nigeria using Aba shoe and bag making model from 2020 to 2024 to examine the impact of vocational education on employment rate and entrepreneurial success are explored in the below table.

Table 1. Research question 2. To what extent does Aba shoe and bag production impact employment rate in Nigeria?

Year	Estimated employed youth	Success rate
2020	50,000	5.3%
2021	80,000	8.6%
2022	100,000	10.8%
2023	200,000	21.5%
2024	500,000	53.8%

Source: President, Leather Product Manufacturers Association Mazi Okechukwu Williams, The PunchNews.

Using the tabulated categories identified above, it is possible to answer the probability that the year 2030 expected percentage of youth employment will be higher if the model experienced critical review and structured by the state and public sectors altogether. The observed recorded percentage of employment as at 2024 is 53.8% out of five (5) predicted years. Using Chi-square analysis, the coming five years is expected to give out the following percentage for youth employment: Observed =

$$x^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$
$$x^2 = \frac{(53.8 - 107.6)^2}{107.6}$$

$$x^2 = \frac{(-53.8)^2}{107.6}$$

$$x^2 = \frac{2894.44}{107.6}$$

$$x^2 = 26.9$$

Therefore, the expected employment rate should be 26.9% added to the recently observed employment rate of 53.8%, given percentage rate of 80.7% expected youth employment by the year 2030 if structured TVET is integrated by government and private sectors at Aba shoe and bag production industry.

1. **Research question 3:** How does this practical TVET models foster long-term economic growth and development in Nigeria?

The figure below presents the yearly percentage and future analysis for sustainable economic development using the statistical summary above.

Fig. 1.

Figure 2, above clearly explained the studied objective showing the implication of practical TVET models on sustainable economic growth as being influenced by skill-based training empowering the youth to be self-reliant and successful entrepreneurs. This strongly depicts the powerful role of Aba shoe and bag production as viable practical TVET model proffering solution to unemployment and as a catalyst for sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Discussion of the findings

The Aba shoe-making industry demonstrates significant employment potential through statistical insight. From institutions like the Footwear Academy in Aba are finding jobs, even internationally. The industry's longevity and creative output, particularly in the leather sector, highlight its established presence. Despite facing challenges, Aba's shoe manufacturers, primarily small and medium enterprises (SMEs), are poised for growth, suggesting ongoing employment opportunities within the sector. The industry's resilience and ability to adapt further contribute to its assumed employment capacity cum year 2030 and beyond. Below includes the major findings of this study:

Ladies hand bag, school children's bags and school bags are produced in Aba and buyers want them nationwide, for instance, Theodon investment Nigeria is a bag maker, manufacturer

and selling firm where one can find all sizes of bags such as school, travelling, shopping, souvenir and man's bags in Aba, Abia state Nigeria.

This TVET model plays a significant role in equipping youth with hands-on skills, bridging the gap between formal education and industry demands. With the bag and shoe production model among others in Aba, Abia state witnessed higher employment rates of 31.6% (NBS, 2020), with many young people transitioning from job-seeking to job creation. In 2016, the Textile, Apparel, and Footwear sector contributed N7 trillion (\$7,078,540,953), exactly 2.1% of Nigeria's total GDP, to Nigeria's economy (NBS, 2020) indicating significant increase in long-term economic growth and development of the nation. A skilled workforce, developed through this effective TVET model, can contribute to socio-economic growth and development by boosting productivity and innovation. Strengthening TVET Partnerships by building strong partnerships between TVET institutions and industry stakeholders can ensure that training programs are relevant and meet the needs of employers. Marketing these locally produced shoes and bags as a viable and attractive pathway for career development can encourage more students to pursue this type of skills. This shoe and bag TVET model can be designed to promote lifelong learning and continuous professional development, allowing individuals to stay up-to-date with industry trends and advancements.

Implications of the study

Social Implications

The shoe and bag production industry in Aba, Abia State Nigeria is a practical TVET in the country that struggle to effectively align with the demands of the local and global labor market, leading to graduates with skills that are not readily employable. Inadequate resources and infrastructure are among the challenges faced as limitations in terms of human and material resources, poor funding hindering the quality of training and overall effectiveness; negative perception of this TVET model by parents and students as a "fallback option," leading to lower enrollment and motivation compared to general education. A lack of strong collaboration between TVET institutions and industry stakeholders can lead to curricula that are not relevant to the needs of employers.

Practical implications

Ensuring long-term funding and sustainable TVET programs is a significant challenge for many African countries (Ikounga, n.d). Government and private sector collaboration in Aba shoe and bag production industry can play a vital role in addressing youth unemployment by providing individuals with the skills and knowledge needed for employment and self-employment.

Conclusion

Unemployment in Nigeria can be tackled through skill-based training in shoe and bag production, which can provide practical skills and enhance employability. These skills are in demand for local economic growth and can lead to viable job opportunities. Shoe and bag production skill-based training can address unemployment by providing access to income-generating opportunities. Traditional apprenticeships in these trades, as highlighted by Onyekwelu (2025) have historically been a pathway to employment. The training offers a practical route to employment and economic empowerment for young people. This skillset is crucial in the leather industry and can lead to employment opportunities or entrepreneurial ventures. Nigeria can address youth unemployment, promote economic development, and improve the lives of its young people by investing in skill-based training in shoe and bag production. This would not only improve the Nigerian economy but could also be leveraged upon by all African countries for sustainable economic development, thereby, fostering long-term economic growth and development in the continent.

Recommendations

1. Addressing youth unemployment and skill gaps by public and private sectors through strengthening shoe and bag production industry are necessary as discovered in this research as a call to improve the quality and relevance of vocational education and training programs aligning them with the needs of the labor market.
2. Promoting entrepreneurship skills by the government and private sectors through providing young people with the resources and support needed to start their own businesses can engender strong empowerment for the young people in shoe and bag production.
3. Offering comprehensive career guidance, counseling and coaching services to help young people identify suitable career paths and acquire the necessary skills is a call from all stakeholder (parents, teachers, and significant other).

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